

CHP and Cogeneration Systems

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Abstract

Technologies of simultaneous production of electricity and heat produce electricity or mechanical power and recycle excess heat for various purposes. It is one of the energy saving methods in which electricity and heat are produced simultaneously. Moreover, the heat obtained from cogeneration can be used for heating purposes in different industries or regions. Several solutions can be proposed to optimize the supplied energy using cogeneration systems. Based on the use, these systems can be built from gas turbines, steam or combustion engines, and regarding primary production energy, fossil fuels, bio-production, geothermal or solar can be used. In this study, we will review the different types of CHP and cogeneration systems and their applications along with the available information and data related to them. An economic comparison is also provided between various CHP methods, which can be a reference for future use in order to improve the efficiency of systems, optimize energy and reduce the production of environmental pollutants.

Keywords: CHP, Cogeneration, Efficiency, Environment, Energy.